

Hello!

On behalf of the Case Amateur Radio Club and the Case School of Engineering, THANK YOU for your participation in the Eclipse CHU Monitoring Project. As previously discussed, due to how your station is in the path of totality, your station has been selected to host three custom receivers for monitoring all three CHU frequencies during the eclipse. We are excited to work with you more on the project, and are deeply appreciative of your help!

Below, you will find the instructions to set up one “ET station.” This is a custom receiver for receiving CHU frequencies, receiving GPS signals (to act as a stable frequency reference), processing the data, and automatically sending the data to us. **Please read the instructions all the way through before starting**, and reach out to us via [the discord server](#) or eclipse-research@case.edu if you have any questions or concerns.

If possible, please provide the following tools. If you don't have them, please reach out to us ASAP and we will work with you to procure them:

- USB-A charger for “topping off” each radio
- USB-A Keyboard and mouse
- HDMI micro cable that can plug into an external monitor
- Screwdriver

Below are the instructions to set up your ET station. **PLEASE FOLLOW THE INSTRUCTIONS IN ORDER AND READ THE ENTIRE MANUAL BEFORE STARTING:**

- 1) Unbox everything! **Please save the packaging** for shipping the receivers back to Ohio upon completion (we will provide the labels).
- 2) Each ET station will have a Raspberry Pi (Label starts with ET), power supply (label starts with LIP), hard drive (label starts with HDD), and XHDATA receiver (label starts with RCV). Each Pi will be assigned to a specific receiver, power supply, and hard drive. You will receive an email telling you which parts should be connected to each other, and this will also be denoted on each receiver and in the packing slips. For example, below, RCV009 should be plugged into ET1012, and ET1012 should be plugged into HDD019 and LIP010.

- 3) "Top off" each XHDATA radio receiver by plugging it into a USB-A charger with the supplied cable. The supplied cable was shipped already plugged into each raspberry pi, so please unplug it to charge and plug it back in upon completion. Please only use the supplied cable or else it may not work. Leave each radio charging for at least 1 hour or

until fully charged.

- 4) In the meantime, locate your raspberry pi with a pre-installed data collection “hat” on top. Do not take the hat off the pi. Connect the raspberry pi to the assigned HDD (Hard Disk Drive). Your raspberry pi should be connected via USB-A via one of the [blue](#) USB-A ports (highlighted below)

- 5) Powering the data collection unit:
 - a) **WARNING: CONNECT THE POWER SUPPLY LEADS TO THE HAT BEFORE PLUGGING THE POWER SUPPLY INTO A WALL OUTLET. IF YOU DO NOT, YOU RISK OF BURNING THE VOLTAGE REGULATOR IN THE HAT.**

- b) **WARNING: DO NOT POWER THE RASPBERRY PI USING ITS USB-C PORT. IT WILL DAMAGE THE HAT.** Only power the Raspberry Pi by using a low-noise 9-16V power supply (like the one we supplied) into the hat.
- c) **WARNING: under normal operation, the Pi should only be powering the radio and hard drive.** Adding additional loads that draw power (such as powering the external monitor) may force the pi to reboot. In step 6b, the mouse and keyboard draw a negligible amount of current so leaving them plugged in is fine.
- d) **BEFORE YOU PLUG THE POWER SUPPLY INTO THE WALL:** Connect the power supply leads to the “PWR” terminal in the hat. The wire with periodic white text on it should be connected to Vin and the wire with a faint stripe on the side should be connected to GND. Tighten the screws.

- e) Upon tightening the screw terminals, and plugging the hard drive in, you can plug in the power supply. After a few moments, the large indicator LED should be magenta (it is ok if it periodically blinks to red).

- 6) Connect the Raspberry Pi to Wifi:

- a) Once the Pi is powered on and confirmed that you see the magenta LED, unplug it from power.
- b) While it is still off, connect the pi to the keyboard, mouse, and monitor. Then, plug the power supply back into power, so it is plugged into the monitor on startup. **Do not power the monitor from the Pi's USB ports and use an external source instead.**
- c) Connect the pi to your local wifi. [Use this article](#). "Setting up Raspberry Pi Wi-Fi via GUI" may be the easiest option for doing this.

- d) You can disconnect the monitor, mouse, and keyboard upon completion. You can also move the system elsewhere. It will automatically reconnect to wifi upon powering on.
- 7) Connect the GPS to the Raspberry Pi hat:
- a) Mount your GPS antenna vertically, ideally near a window sill or outside as it is waterproof. The top should be pointed upwards. Mounting the GPS antenna can be done before the rest of the setup.
 - b) Screw the GPS antenna into the connector for the data collection unit as shown below. Do not worry about the extra lock washers/lock nuts on the SMA

connector.

- c) After no longer than two minutes, the red LED labeled “FIX” on the GPS module should blink once every 15 seconds instead of once every second. This signals that the unit successfully found a GPS fix. The large indicator LED should switch from magenta to green. It is ok if the green LED periodically changes to red for a few seconds and switches back to green.

8) Build and pitch your antenna.

- a) This can be done before you set up the rest of the data collection units. For each ET unit, we supplied 25 feet of wire and a terminal block. The wire can easily be replaced by going to the hardware store and getting more if needed (22AWG or close). Get creative here!
- b) Please reach out to Adam or the discord for any questions about how/where to pitch a random wire antenna. Below, see W8EDU's vertical antenna (out of a third story window and spaced away from the concrete wall with scrap wood). The wire is hanging off the wood with zip ties. The wood is secured by drilling a hole into it and running paracord through the hole. We tied the paracord to a table.

9) Connect the receiver to antenna through the “ant” jack

10) Connect Pi to radio (audio and USB)

- a) Unplug the radio from the USB-A charger
- b) Plug the audio cable into the jack of the radio with a headphone icon

- c) Screw the audio cable into the hat's screw terminals. The red wire should be plugged into "Audio" and Grey should be plugged into "GND"

- d) Plug the USB charger cable into one of the remaining blue ports into the Raspberry Pi. **WHILE THE PI IS RUNNING AND POWERED ON**, plug the other

end into the radio to keep it “topped off.”

- e) Turn radio on and confirm it is on the right frequency. We will email you which receiver should be on each frequency. In this case, the receiver is set to 7850 kHz.

- f) Turn the volume on the radio to full using the Volume knob on the side. To confirm the radio works and that it is receiving, you can unplug the audio jack and with any luck hear CHU ticks. However, there is a chance that propagation will dampen the ticks, and you may not be able to hear it during the specific conditions you are in.

11) Notify of completion. Let the team know and we will confirm that it is streaming data!

- a) If the indicator LED switches to magenta, re-adjust the GPS antenna so it turns back to green
- b) If the indicator LED switches to white, please contact Adam and I will work you through troubleshooting.
- c) You can check the status of your receiver and see the recordings it is taking of each second tick in the time domain using [this website](#)